

Honey Production from Forest

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Beehives installed within agroforestry systems in Galicia (NW Spain)

The EU is the second largest honey producer in the world, with an annual production of around 250,000 tonnes. Moreover, honey production is the main forest farming activity promoted across Europe by National Apiculture Programs and Rural Development Programmes, mainly due to the crucial role that honeybee colonies play in plant pollination. In this context, honey production integrated into agroforestry systems can enhance cross-pollination and, therefore, increase crop yields while also contributing to food and income security for people living in rural areas. On the other hand, it is important to be aware that apiculture does not require full-time labour, and each hive requires only around 2-3 m² of space. Regarding hives management, beehives can be installed isolated or in groups of 30 or 40, placed off the ground, protected from north winds, and positioned with the bees' entrance and exit facing southwest. In the spring, beehives should be fed periodically with a nutritional supplement based on proteins, amino acids, vitamins and minerals. In October, after honey extraction from beehives, treatment for Varroa should be applied, followed by maintenance feeding according to each hive's needs until spring. In general, one hive produces around 15 kg of honey, and 1kg of honey sells for 10 €, which can provide a sustainable source of income for farmers, reduce financial risks, and promote economic resilience in rural communities.

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